

accelerate
futureHEI
supporting future focused higher education

D5.2 Capacity Building Program:
Delivery progress report and updated plan

30.06.2025

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List of abbreviations

HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ITAP	Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package
CEU	Continuing Education Unit
UBC	University-Business Collaboration
ESD	Education For Sustainable Development

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Project Consortium

University Industry Innovation Network BV (UIIN) - Netherlands

TUM International GMBH (TUMInt) - Germany

Momentum Marketing Services Limited (MMS) - Ireland

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST) - Portugal

Universite De La Reunion (UR) – La Reunion, France

Universidad Europea De Canarias (UEC) – Canary Islands, Spain

Universidade da Madeira (UMa) – Madeira, Portugal

Fachhochschule St. Polten GMBH (STPUAS) - Austria

UC Leuven (UCLL) - Belgium

Magyar Agrar- Es Elettudományi Egyetem (MATE) - Hungary

Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara (UPT) - Romania

Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA) - Latvia

In the project, the university partners are represented by or focus the project work on unique departments across their institutions. Specifically:

- UEC: School of Architecture
- UMa: *Higher School of Technology and Management*.
- STPUAS: team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer
- UCLL: Business Management and Research & Expertise
- MATE: Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics
- ViA: management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences
- IST: Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment
- UR: ESIROI engineering school
- UPT: Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre

Executive Summary: Capacity Building Program

What is this project about?

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), the **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate Future HEI project) will develop and test acceleration services to equip universities with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative. The project will apply a comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with a tailored transformation action project (ITAPs).

How does this project support universities?

What is this deliverable about?

This interim deliverable provides a progress report on the Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program being implemented as part of the Accelerate Future HEI project. It responds to the guiding question: *“How to best support the testing partners, based on their evolving skills needs and challenges during the testing and implementation of the ITAPs?”*

The report outlines the training activities conducted since the program's launch in January 2024, including the courses delivered across six training domains, participation metrics, and insights from feedback collected through participant questionnaires and interviews. It also reflects on the alignment between the original training objectives—identified through WP2 Current State Analysis and WP3 Roadmap Workshops—and the training program delivered so far.

In addition, this deliverable presents an updated plan for the remainder of the program, identifying opportunities to expand and adapt the learning framework.

01

Project Overview, Aim & Approach

An overview of the project's overarching goals, objectives, methodology and consortium.

Project Overview

The **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate_FutureHEI; thereafter referred as Accelerate Future HEI) project, under the coordination of [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), launched in January 2023 and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe program.

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services for institutional transformation.

Main Aim

Accelerate Future HEI aims to **develop and test acceleration services to equip Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative.** To do that Accelerate Future HEI will apply a robust, comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with tailored institutional transformation acceleration projects (ITAPs). Participating in this initiative provides the HEIs with a unique opportunity to identify key challenges they are facing and dedicate time and resources to develop solutions through unique ITAPs.

Through this project, the HEIs are not doing this alone, but instead receive personalised and peer-to-peer guidance through access to coaches, thematic working group workshops, training workshops and cohort knowledge exchange events. This allows HEIs to take a close internal look at what they want to achieve while receiving external support and guidance to enable them to implement these changes.

Key Objectives

IDENTIFY

the status quo of each HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects

BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs' staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through **a skills development program.**

EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'Acceleration Board' of **independent experts.**

GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Project Consortium

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), this ambitious project brings together twelve European partners from eleven countries to develop and implement acceleration services. The project consortium unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia, one from the EIT HEI initiative (INCORE) and one from the European University Alliance (E³UDRES²) and EIT HEI Initiative (E.I.N.S). UIIN, together with TUM International and Momentum are referred to as *acceleration partners* to design and deliver the acceleration services and support the HEI *testing partners* as they implement their initiatives.

Our consortium represents institutions across Europe, including the Outermost Regions. The diversity of the partners will enable the development of overarching services that can be applied in different contexts and enable the HEIs to impact their regions.

Project Approach & Methodology

The project's methodology is based on a **gap analysis** which involves a **three-phase approach** to understand the context, strategy, goals and status quo of each HEI testing partner and to provide an evidence-base and solid starting point to identifying areas and opportunities for institutional transformation. The research, development and implementation phases are underpinned and supported by training, evaluation, dissemination and other activities across the project duration.

Current State Analysis

WP2 | M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation.

Where are HEIs now?

The aim of this phase is to (1) clarify the desired future state and goals for institutional transformation and (2) understand the current state of each HEI testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the partner universities. Specifically, WP2 involves activities of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus groups, and survey. The survey findings will be explored in depth in this report.

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs

WP3 | M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

Subsequently this phase builds on the current state data to define and design an implementation plan to achieve the desired future state and institutional transformation goals and objectives, with regards to entrepreneurial and innovative activities including the identification of opportunities and challenges to address in acceleration services and coaching activities. This will be done through the roadmap workshops as well as Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs).

Acceleration services pilot-testing

WP4 | M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

This phase will support the testing partners in implementing the acceleration services and undertake actions towards institutional change, through a mixture of individual HEI and group-based support. Specifically, HEIs will undergo individual ITAP coaching with experts aligned to their core transformation focus areas, to then work on the implementation of their ITAPs and development of their investment strategy.

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program

WP5 | M1 – M48

HEIs will be supported with knowledge exchange and learning opportunities across the full duration of the project. In addition to the personalised coaching sessions, and the feedback, peer-to-peer feedback and mentoring guidance, which will be provided throughout *Phase 1* and *Phase 2*, HEIs will have access to dedicated events and workshops, including thematic Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events and Accelerate Training Workshops.

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation

WP6 | M1 – M48

The progress of the ITAPs will be tracked through a dedicated monitoring and evaluation mechanism to evaluate the impact and policy implications.

Communication and Dissemination

WP7 | M1 – M48

A communication and dissemination plan will be developed to share the transformation stories and the project's key learnings to benefit the project's community.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback

WP1 | M1 – M48

Adequate management and quality assurance processes and tools will be developed to deliver on the project's outcomes and inform policy.

Foundational conceptual model

The methodology within this project is based on a combination of research and practice. One of the key models underpinning the methodology is the **UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]** - the framework has been developed over 10 years of research and validated in practice to define the key elements of an entrepreneurial and innovative university, and the challenges and success factors associated with HEI transformation to become more entrepreneurial, innovative and engaged.

UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]

Main Deliverables

An overview of the main deliverables are outlined below, with the current delivered report highlighted.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48

The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy

D1.1
DMP M6

D1.2
Initial policy briefing M12

D1.3
Interim policy briefing M30

D1.4
Final policy recommendations report M48

Current State Analysis M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?

D2.1
Strategic Vision Statements – M12

D2.2
Synthesis Report – M12

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

D3.1
Roadmaps Analysis report - Draft M12

D3.2
Roadmaps Analysis report - Final M18

Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

D4.1
Summary report - common ITAP issues M12

D4.2
Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48

The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation

D5.1
Program overview & delivery plan M12

D5.2
Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30

D5.3
Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48

We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs

D6.1
Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12

D6.2
ITAPs Progress report – M30

D6.3
Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48

We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit

D7.1
Initial Plan M6

D7.2
Updated plan & first dissemination report M12

D7.3
Interim dissemination report M30

D7.4
Final dissemination report M48

02

Overview of the Accelerate Training Program

Program design and training domains

Training program design - recap

The program aims to **grow institutional capacity by building the skills and competencies** of leadership, academic, and professional staff, through a structured training offer and collaborative knowledge exchange.

From challenges and needs to skills

Based on the Current State Analysis (WP2; read more in D2.2 Synthesis Report: Key findings on current state analysis) and the Roadmap Workshops, undertaken in WP3, **four key themes of challenges and opportunities** (read more in D3.1 Common challenges and solutions to becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative HEIs) for the institutional transformation towards a more engaged, entrepreneurial, and innovative university have been identified:

- **Entrepreneurial skills and mindset of students**, including fostering entrepreneurial skills and mindset among students going beyond traditional academic knowledge.
- **Impactful research and research valorisation** - envisioning and planning for research that goes beyond academic curiosity, in alignment with valorisation efforts to address real-world challenges.
- **Institutional support for engagement and innovation** through fostering support structures and institutional commitment, as well as capacity building for professional staff that facilitate support to entrepreneurial education and research
- **Partnership strategies for stronger engagement** through collaborative relationships and partnerships between university and regional and international external stakeholders in government, civic society and industry.

Defining training domains

Stemming from the above mentioned four themes, UIIN identified **six training domains** to address the skill needs and challenges of different target groups across the nine testing partners. The training domains are classified as:

- Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development
- Impactful research and research valorisation
- Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement
- Entrepreneurial development of the university
- Regional innovation hubs
- Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

Defining target groups

The six training domains reflect the needs and challenges of three different stakeholder groups and therefore different training programs will target the different groups, specifically:

- **Professional staff** involved in business development, partnerships, university-industry engagement or entrepreneurship / valorisation
- **Leadership** involved in innovation, enterprise development, university-industry engagement, impact or entrepreneurship/valorisation
- Education and/ or research focused **academics** interested in learning more about entrepreneurship, impact, industry engagement and valorisation (open to early, mid-career or senior academics, including PhD students)

In the next section a more detailed explanation about the six domains and examples of the courses that are being offered is provided.

Training program Framework:

Six training domains

Based on the identified needs of the nine testing partners, six training domains have been established for academic staff, professional services, and institutional leadership. Each domain includes clearly defined learning objectives, relevant target groups, and a selection of courses.

1

Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development

Tailored specifically for education-focused academics and faculty, this comprehensive training domain is designed to empower academics and educators with the tools and strategies needed to cultivate an entrepreneurial and innovative mindset among students. This training aspires to promote **educators' competencies**, so they not only are well-versed in **designing entrepreneurial curricula** and **utilising multidisciplinary education practices** but also capable of shaping the next generation of entrepreneurial leaders, through **supporting student entrepreneurship**, and integrating **sustainable development goals into education**.

2

Impactful research and research valorisation

The second training domain targets research-focused academics and faculty, and aims to equip them with the skills and knowledge necessary to extend the influence of their **research beyond traditional academic boundaries**, and explore **different research valorisation possibilities**. The key learning objectives further encompass **building compelling research communication skills** for research impact, along with skills to **integrate sustainable development goals into research** and encourage more interdisciplinary connections to enhance the impact and societal relevance of research endeavours.

3

Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement

The third domain proposes a training program focused on professional staff and leadership. In an era marked by the interconnectedness of academic institutions and their broader ecosystems, this program is designed to equip participants with the **skills and strategies needed to cultivate meaningful partnerships and amplify external engagement**. The learning objectives include the establishment of collaborations between universities and their extended R&I ecosystem, while **maximising the impact** and **turning transactional relationships into transformative partnerships**. The program is specifically curated to support professional staff and leadership in **facilitating academics with building relationships with external stakeholders** and developing efficient processes for **mapping and evaluating collaborations**.

4

Entrepreneurial development of the university

In recognition of the transformative potential that entrepreneurialism holds for HEIs, the fourth training domain is crafted to empower professional staff with the **knowledge and tools necessary to foster an entrepreneurial culture within their universities**. The envisioned learning objectives revolve around **best practices for professional staff to help faculty build their entrepreneurial capacity, effectively valorise their research or initiate business ventures**. Moreover, the courses aim to delve into the development of **balanced and diverse career pathways** for academics, exploring the concept of an engaged university, and **embedding entrepreneurialism into the university's overarching strategy** and communication strategy.

5

Regional innovation hubs

The fifth training domain is carefully designed for professional staff and leadership that are interested in **creating hubs and launch pads that serve as one-stop shops for entrepreneurship**, acting as catalysts for seamless collaborations. The program will guide participants through the most important elements of **establishing innovation hubs** within the surrounding ecosystem. By participating in this training, professional staff and leadership will gain practical insights and tools to strategically position their institution at the forefront of regional innovation, while raising the awareness of their university's contribution to the **development of the surrounding ecosystem**.

6

Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

The sixth training domain is designed with the focus on university leaders and senior management seeking to **cultivate an environment of innovation and entrepreneurship** within their institutions. This domain is strategically curated to empower leaders with the proactive skills needed to **foster an entrepreneurial culture and driving transformative initiatives**. By participating in this training, leaders will gain insights and practical tools to create overarching sustainability strategies and effecting supporting structures that will steer their institutions towards a desired future marked by enduring innovative and entrepreneurial engagement.

Training Approach

Drawing on the Current State Analysis (WP2) and key challenges identified in WP3, UIIN designed and has been delivering a range of courses to equip academics, professional staff and leaders within the testing partner HEIs with the skills needed to implement their ITAPs and drive change within their institutions.

As each HEI is different, it is important that the training approach is adaptable and flexible to the different needs. The training approach developed by UIIN has two unique aspects: (1) **flexible and diverse learning formats** to cater for multiple learning styles and (2) **a modular delivery framework**, to allow for customisable learning journeys.

Learning formats

To allow for interactivity, international and inter-institutional networking as well as effective learning, a flexible online learning format is being applied throughout the training. The delivery, timeframe and frequency of sessions will be tailored to meet testing partners' availability and commitments throughout the remaining time of the project.

Participants are being equipped with the tools, resources and knowledge to enhance their understanding, analyse their own activities and develop concrete next steps for implementing their learnings in their daily work, all contributing to the strategic vision set previously in the project (WP2; read more in D2.1 Strategic Vision Statements towards becoming Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities) and the ITAPs that have been developed in WP3 and are being implemented in WP4.

To cater for different **learning styles, schedules and expertise levels**, the program is being delivered in a flexible learning format. The training program features include:

- **Diverse session formats:** UIIN uses a variety of delivery formats (explained in more detail on the next page) to foster an ideal environment for comprehending theoretical concepts, learning from good practice examples and implementing real-life skills.
- **Live and self-paced:** Workshops and knowledge to practice sessions require live participation, which encourages active collaboration and peer learning. Assignments and seminars offer the flexibility to be completed at the participants' own pace.
- **Globally sourced materials:** Participants have access to an array of published materials such as reports, articles, podcasts and instructional videos to supplement their learnings. These resources provide opportunities for in-depth exploration of topics covered during the course.

All the sessions are being delivered online via Zoom. The learning materials, assignments and peer reviews are accessible via a personal learning environment managed by UIIN.

Certification Model

UIIN applies the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) framework, recognising learning and skill development through the Continuing Education Units (CEUs) system. One CEU is awarded for every eight hours of active learning.

Participants who successfully complete a course within the Accelerate Training Program receive a UIIN micro-credential in the form of a shareable digital badge. In addition, they are awarded 1.5 CEUs, which can contribute towards obtaining a recognised professional certification.

Modularity and engagement

UIIN's training offerings are structured as modular courses. These courses can be taken individually as stand-alone learning opportunities or grouped into thematic tracks as part of a broader training program, aligned to the six identified domains. The modular approach has been deliberately chosen as the foundation for learning delivery, as it enables customisable learning pathways. This structure allows participants to select the courses that best address their specific skill development needs while ensuring the content is concise, focused, and easy to apply in practice.

A **course is a self-contained learning unit** designed to address a specific topic through a **mix of learning modalities**. The courses are structured to provide an engaging and effective learning experience, making use of a variety of formats. The learning modalities that have been incorporated in the Accelerate Training Program include:

Interactive workshops

A mix of theory and facilitated discussions as well as hands-on activities allowing participants to co-create with peers.

Knowledge-to-practice sessions

Collaborative sessions under expert guidance, applying the gained knowledge to practice.

Fireside chats

Informal interviews with field experts sharing their unique perspectives.

Individual and peer-reviewed reflections

Short assignments to contribute and receive valuable feedback from others.

Course assignments

Self-paced, peer-reviewed assignments to test the acquired knowledge and apply the new skills in real-life scenarios.

Self-paced resources

Course material and supporting resources like articles, case studies, podcasts and videos to supplement learning.

An example course may include the following components:

- **One or two guided interactive workshops** (2 hours each), combining theory, case studies, group discussions, and short interactive exercises.
- **One or two Fireside Chats** with invited experts, offering insights and real-world perspectives.
- **One practical session** (1 to 1.5 hours) designed to help participants apply their knowledge through a structured, interactive group assignment.

03

Delivery Progress

Overview of training activities delivered, participation so far, and key feedback from testing partners

Overview of the Accelerate Training Program to Date

The Accelerate Training Program was launched in January 2024 and will continue throughout the duration of the project. It is designed to offer flexible and targeted capacity-building opportunities for staff in testing partner universities, across leadership, academic, and professional roles.

Testing partners are regularly updated on newly developed and upcoming courses. At the same time, they are responsible for running internal awareness campaigns to ensure the training opportunities reach relevant stakeholders within their institutions. Participation in the program is closely monitored. Comprehensive attendance data—including registration and completion figures—can be found in Annex 1 of this report.

The section below provides an overview of the courses being delivered. Each course is accompanied by a brief description. To complement this overview, the chapter also presents participant feedback, offering insights into the perceived value of the training, its practical application, and the challenges it has helped to address.

Key Figures of the Accelerate Training Program

Since its launch, the Accelerate Training Program has delivered a wide range of learning opportunities to university staff, supported by external experts. Table 1 below summarises the key numbers demonstrating the scale and reach of the program to date, including participation levels, the number of courses and workshops delivered, and the involvement of experts and stakeholders across different roles.

Table 1. Accelerate Training program – key numbers

Courses and Thematic Alignment

The Accelerate Training Program is designed around a modular structure, with courses grouped under six thematic domains that reflect priority areas for institutional development. These domains provide a coherent framework that allows participants to select learning opportunities relevant to their institutional needs and professional roles.

Table 2 below presents the full set of courses currently offered as part of the program, along with their alignment to the six domains: **Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development (D1)**, **Impactful research and research valorisation (D2)**, **Holistic partnership strategies and stronger external engagement (D3)**, **Entrepreneurial development of the university (D4)**, **Regional innovation hubs (D5)**, and **Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership (D6)**.

Course	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6
Navigating your Partnership Landscape			✓			
Initiating and Developing a Partnership			✓			
Going from Transactional to Strategic Partnerships			✓			
Fundamentals of Sustainable Universities				✓	✓	✓
Developing Entrepreneurial Education	✓					
Maximising Impact through Effective Partnership Management		✓	✓			
Building Start-ups at Universities				✓		
Towards university-business cooperation vision and culture			✓			✓
Education-Driven University-Business Cooperation	✓		✓			
Nurturing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems		✓		✓	✓	
Measuring Impact of University-Business Collaboration			✓	✓		
Impactful researchers		✓				

Table 2. Accelerate Training program – overview of the courses available

Description of the courses

A detailed overview of the courses delivered to date is provided below. Each course is made up of a combination of **interactive workshops (W)**, **Fireside Chats with external experts (FSC)**, and **Knowledge to Practice sessions (KtP)**, designed to provide participants with both theoretical insights and practical application opportunities.

1

Navigating your Partnership Landscape

- *Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding (W)*
- *External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding (W)*
- *Leveraging assets for partnerships (FSC)*
- *Asset mapping (KtP)*

This course supports participants in analysing and understanding their institution's partnership ecosystem. It focuses on identifying internal capacities and external stakeholders relevant to developing effective university–industry collaborations.

2

Initiating and Developing a Partnership

- *Identifying and evaluating partners (W)*
- *Crafting your partnership approach (W)*
- *How proximity and co-location drive innovation (FSC)*
- *Evaluating external partners (KtP)*

This course develops participants' skills to initiate collaborative partnerships aligned with institutional priorities. It addresses partnership drivers, stakeholder mapping, and initial engagement strategies.

This course has been delivered twice.

3

Going from Transactional to Strategic Partnerships

- *Strategic partnership models and frameworks (W)*
- *Negotiation and partnership agreements (W)*
- *Multistakeholder partnership (FSC)*
- *Building your partnership framework (KtP)*

This course focuses on advancing institutional collaboration from short-term, transactional interactions to long-term, strategic partnerships. Participants examine models and frameworks that support the development of high-value partnerships aligned with institutional goals. The course covers key principles of negotiation and the structuring of partnership agreements.

This course has been delivered twice.

4

Fundamentals of Sustainable Universities

- *A whole-institution approach (W)*
- *University pathways to sustainability (W)*
- *Role of universities in advancing sustainability (FSC)*
- *Creating an action plan (KtP)*

This course introduces key concepts and approaches for embedding sustainability in university operations and strategies. Participants define institutional goals, identify enablers, and co-create pathways toward sustainable transformation.

This course has been delivered twice.

5

Developing Entrepreneurial Education

- *Developing student employability through entrepreneurship (W)*
- *Creating excellent entrepreneurship education (W)*
- *Effective entrepreneurial pedagogies (KtP)*
- *Best practice in entrepreneurship education (FSC)*
- *Design an entrepreneurship course (KtP)*

This course provides participants with practical tools and approaches to enhance entrepreneurship education within their institutions. It explores strategies to foster student employability, develop high-quality entrepreneurship curricula, and apply effective entrepreneurial pedagogies. Through expert insights and applied exercises, participants gain the knowledge and confidence to design or improve entrepreneurship courses tailored to their institutional context.

This course has been delivered twice.

6

Maximising Impact through Effective Partnership Management

- *Managing Partnerships Governance (W)*
- *Measuring and Evaluating Partnerships (W)*
- *Account Management and CRM (FsC)*
- *Develop a Partnership health check (KtP)*

This course supports participants in strengthening the governance and operational management of institutional partnerships. It explores governance structures, decision-making processes, and coordination mechanisms that enable effective collaboration. Additionally, the training addresses how well-managed partnerships can contribute to the delivery of high-quality entrepreneurship education, enhancing both institutional impact and value creation for external stakeholders.

7

Building Start-ups at Universities

- *Setting up for student entrepreneurship success (W)*
- *Supporting student start-ups and beyond (W)*
- *Virtual visit to an entrepreneurship hub (FSC)*
- *The principles for a successful university incubator or entrepreneurship centre (W)*
- *Developing a university incubator, unit or program (KtP)*

This course focuses on the institutional structures and strategies that enable student entrepreneurship. Participants explore how to create supportive environments for early-stage ventures, including guidance services, mentorship, and funding access. The course also examines the core components of effective university incubators and entrepreneurship centres, providing frameworks for their setup, governance, and long-term sustainability.

8

Towards university-business cooperation vision and culture

- *Building a vision for engagement (W)*
- *Turning vision into reality (FsC)*
- *Championing UBC culture (W)*
- *Creating a culture change plan (KtP)*

This course supports institutions in developing a clear strategic vision for university–business cooperation (UBC). Participants examine how to align external engagement with institutional missions and long-term goals. The training also focuses on fostering a collaborative organisational culture by identifying internal champions, addressing cultural barriers, and embedding UBC principles across academic and professional functions.

9

Education-Driven University-Business Cooperation

- *Embedding industry in education (W)*
- *Innovative pedagogies for impactful education (W)*
- *Positioning education driven UBC (KtP)*
- *Learning from best practices (FSC)*

This course focuses on strengthening the role of external stakeholders—particularly industry partners—in higher education. Participants examine models for embedding business collaboration in curriculum design, teaching, and assessment. The training also introduces innovative pedagogical approaches that support experiential learning and improve the relevance and impact of educational programs.

This course has been delivered twice.

10

Nurturing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems

- *Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (W)*
- *Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship (W)*
- *The role of universities (FSC)*
- *Mapping your entrepreneurial ecosystem (KtP)*

This course guides participants in analysing and strengthening their university's role within a broader entrepreneurial ecosystem. It focuses on identifying key ecosystem actors, resources, and dynamics. Participants explore strategies to support collaboration, align institutional capabilities with regional needs, and foster an environment that enables entrepreneurship across disciplines and sectors.

11

Measuring Impact of University-Business Collaboration

- *Creating culture of engagement (FSC)*
- *Measuring Collaboration Outputs, Outcomes and Impact (W)*
- *Communicating Impact of Collaborations (W)*
- *Mapping pathway to impact (KtP)*

This course equips participants with tools and frameworks for assessing the effectiveness of university–business collaboration. It covers methodologies for tracking outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts. Participants also examine how to structure agreements that support measurable collaboration goals and develop strategies to communicate the impact of partnerships to internal and external stakeholders.

12

Impactful Researchers

- *Setting up for impactful research (W)*
- *Impact mindset (W)*
- *Communicating research and its impact (W)*
- *Creating a personal brand (W)*
- *Setting up for external engagement success (W)*
- *Valorisation pathways (w)*

This course is designed to support researchers in strengthening the societal and institutional impact of their work. Developed in response to ongoing feedback from testing partners, the course addresses the diverse needs and professional profiles of academic staff through six focused workshops.

Participants engage with key themes such as developing an impact-oriented research mindset, planning for societal relevance, and identifying valorisation pathways. The program also covers strategies for building a strong personal research brand, effective communication of research outcomes, and preparing for successful external engagement.

Participant Feedback

As part of the ongoing implementation of the Accelerate Training Program, participants were invited to share reflections on their learning experiences via a follow-up survey and short qualitative interviews. The questionnaire aimed to capture the perceived value of the training, how the content has been applied in practice, and the challenges that participants were able to address as a result of their involvement.

The feedback received indicates a **high level of engagement and relevance** across the various stakeholder groups, including leadership, academic, and professional staff. Respondents highlighted several courses as particularly impactful, such as those focused on partnership development, sustainability, and entrepreneurial mindsets.

Participants reported that the program provided them with **practical frameworks and inspiration** for advancing institutional transformation in their own contexts. They noted the value of learning from peer institutions and hearing real-world success stories, which helped to frame strategic challenges in a new light. Several respondents emphasised that the training supported them in developing or refining institutional strategies, particularly in relation to external partnerships and long-term engagement models.

In terms of **application**, participants shared how they had integrated learnings into teaching, partnership planning, and curriculum development. Some noted the influence of the training on their approach to long-term institutional ecosystem building, particularly in support of entrepreneurial or interdisciplinary initiatives.

The responses also revealed some **challenges** that the training helped to address, including stakeholder engagement, internal awareness building, and time management for capacity

development activities. One respondent, for example, mentioned that the training contributed to structuring a more comprehensive internal partnership strategy.

Overall, the feedback affirms the **relevance and usefulness** of the training content while also pointing to areas for continuous improvement—such as managing course workload, ensuring practical engagement, and expanding stakeholder inclusion (e.g., student perspectives). This input will inform the refinement of the program as outlined in the updated delivery plan.

Participant Quotes

- *“Developing Entrepreneurial Minds was an opportunity to think deeply about the role of the university in fostering innovation.”*
- *“I’ve been able to apply what I’ve learned to support our international partnership strategy and improve internal coordination.”*
- *“The examples of how other universities approach entrepreneurship were very valuable — it was inspiring and directly applicable.”*
- *“The course helped me to structure a more complete ecosystem for my School, especially around long-term partnerships.”*
- *“It was helpful to see how different institutions adapt to their context. It gave me concrete ideas I could take back.”*
- *“I use the knowledge I gained when planning initiatives with stakeholders — it made me more confident in those discussions.”*

Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events

In addition to the Accelerate Training Program, a key element of WP5 is the organisation of **Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events**. These biannual events bring together testing partners to foster peer learning, mutual support, and collective reflection on institutional transformation. Each session is designed around the current stage of implementation and the emerging challenges across partner institutions.

The Cohort Knowledge Exchanges events are **held every 6 months**, providing testing partners with the opportunity to collaborate and connect with one another. Testing partners are able to **openly share** their findings, learnings, and best practices, while also gaining valuable insights from their peers. Additionally, these events serve as a **meeting place** where testing partners can connect with various ecosystem actors, such as investors and public funders. This **facilitates meaningful discussions**, networking opportunities, and potential collaborations that can further enhance the impact and success of the cohort's initiatives.

Since the project's launch, five events have been organised:

- **June 2023 (online)** – The first event focused on helping testing partners articulate their **Strategic Vision Statements**. The event featured an interactive workshop facilitated by UIIN, where partners worked collaboratively to define their long-term transformation goals (more in D2.1).
- **January 2024 (Munich)** – this event hosted alongside the TPM, combined peer exchange with a site visit to **Munich Urban Colab**, one of the city's key innovation hubs. Participants engaged in co-creation sessions for their Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs) and visited leading research and commercialisation facilities including **GATE** and **TUMint Energy Research**.

- **September 2024 (Online)** – A virtual event aligned with the online TPM. This session revisited ITAP progress and encouraged collaborative refinement of strategies based on early feedback and evaluation insights.
- **January 2025 (Tenerife)** – Hosted by project partners at Universidad Europea de Canarias, this event was embedded within the midpoint partner meeting. Partners met with **local stakeholders**, including **CEOE Tenerife** and the **EUC School of Sustainability**, and explored local innovation initiatives such as those led by **COACTFE Arquitectos**. Sessions focused on storytelling, impact measurement, and fostering institutional transformation through ecosystem engagement.
- **Planned – October 2025 (Joint event with Interreg)** – The next event is being prepared as a **joint initiative with the Interreg project community**, further strengthening links between Accelerate and other European innovation ecosystems. The focus is expected to include cross-project knowledge sharing and policy feedback.

Each **Cohort Knowledge Exchange Event** continues to build a collaborative environment where testing partners can **share learnings, identify common challenges, and co-develop actionable solutions**. These events are critical in reinforcing the community of practice that underpins Accelerate Future HEI's transformation agenda.

04

Reflections and Next Steps

From Insights to Action:
Strengthening and Evolving the
Training Programme

Strengths, Gaps and Improvement Areas

The first phase of the Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Programme has demonstrated strong potential to support institutional transformation across diverse higher education contexts. Testing partners have responded positively to the programme's flexibility, the relevance of its thematic focus, and the modular training design that allows tailored participation by academic, professional, and leadership staff.

Key strengths include:

- A clear structure aligned with institutional transformation goals
- A well-balanced offer of live, asynchronous, and peer-learning formats
- The diversity of course topics supporting both strategic and operational priorities

However, a number of challenges and improvement areas have also emerged during implementation. One of the most significant is ensuring consistent and broad-based **stakeholder engagement** across all partner institutions. Despite internal promotion efforts, participation has varied depending on institutional structures, competing priorities, and internal communication capacity.

Language barriers have posed another practical limitation for some stakeholders, particularly among staff not routinely engaged in international activities. This has sometimes restricted engagement to more senior or internationally experienced groups.

Finally, feedback has highlighted opportunities to improve the **practical application and accessibility** of content, including:

- Managing workload expectations during course periods
- Providing more context-specific examples
- Ensuring opportunities for all institutional roles, including students, to engage where relevant

These insights have directly informed the refinement of the programme's delivery strategy, detailed below.

Updated Delivery Plan and Training Continuation Strategy

In response to the reflections above, the next stage of the programme will focus on enhancing impact, increasing accessibility, and maintaining the programme's ability to adapt to partner needs. The training will continue to be structured around the six original thematic domains, while remaining open to **new topics that may arise** from the ongoing implementation of ITAPs or broader developments in the higher education landscape.

To extend the depth and relevance of the programme, **external experts** will be brought in to deliver targeted workshops on specialised topics such as **engaged leadership, systemic change, and institutional innovation**. These sessions will complement the UIIN-led training catalogue and allow partners to engage with a broader range of perspectives and practical frameworks.

Delivery formats will remain mixed – combining live online sessions, asynchronous self-paced content, and cohort-based knowledge exchange events. This approach provides flexibility for institutions to select learning opportunities aligned with their context and strategic objectives.

UIIN will continue to issue a **quarterly training calendar**, enabling partners to promote upcoming sessions internally and invite participation from relevant staff. Courses will continue to be accredited using the **Continuing Education Unit (CEU)** model, with successful participants receiving **1.5 CEUs and a UIIN-issued digital micro-credential** per course.

Throughout the remainder of the project, the programme will remain anchored in **ongoing feedback and active engagement** with testing partners. This ensures that content remains relevant, delivery formats remain accessible, and the overall training offer continues to support institutional transformation across the consortium.

Annex 1

List of registrations

Participants

note: add a new entry for each participation

Participant name	Institution	Position	Target group	Registered	Participated	Workshop	Workshop #
Arnold Csonka	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Birgit Kaiser	STPUAS	Team Member European University Executive Office	Professional staff	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Emese Pihoda	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Iveta Putnina	VIA	Vice Rector	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Khalid Addi	UR	Deputy Director	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Nuno Almeida	IST	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Internal Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	1
Khalid Addi	UR	Deputy Director	HEI leaders	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Arnold Csonka	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Emese Pihoda	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Iveta Putnina	VIA	Vice Rector	HEI leaders	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Nuno Almeida	IST	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	External Ecosystem: mapping and understanding	2
Beatriz Mendes	IST	Corporate Partnership Unit Coordinator	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Carla Patrocínio	IST	Head of the Technology Transfer Office of Institute	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Catarina Ferreira	IST	Technology Transfer office	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Cátia Pires	IST	Administrative assistant	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Katrien Vandael	UCLL	Researcher Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Marguerite Vatiér	UR	Consultant Innovation and Health	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Khalid Addi	UR	Professor	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Linda Krumina	VIA	Lifelong Learning Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Rita Favas	IST	Corporate Partnerships Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identifying and evaluating partners	3
Beatriz Mendes	IST	Corporate Partnership Unit Coordinator	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Carla Patrocínio	IST	Head of the Technology Transfer Office of Institute	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Catarina Ferreira	IST	Technology Transfer office	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Cátia Pires	IST	Administrative assistant	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Katrien Vandael	UCLL	Researcher Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Khalid Addi	UR	Professor	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Linda Krumina	VIA	Lifelong Learning Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Rita Favas	IST	Corporate Partnerships Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Crafting your partnership approach	4
Liga Cvetkova	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Zane Kudure	VIA	Science Secretary	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Laura Fisere	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Liene Golča	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Liga Cvetkova	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Zane Kudure	VIA	Science Secretary	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Liene Golča	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Linda Krumina	VIA	Lifelong Learning project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Linda Krumina	VIA	Lifelong Learning project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Māriete Balanuka	VIA	International Project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Māriete Balanuka	VIA	International Project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Inés Flores-Colen	IST	Full Professor - Vice-Head of Department	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities	7
Inés Flores-Colen	IST	Full Professor - Vice-Head of Department	HEI leaders	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many routes"	8
Lotte Ovaere	UCLL	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities	7
Lotte Ovaere	UCLL	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many routes"	8
KatrienWandael	UCLL	Researcher Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities	7
KatrienWandael	UCLL	Researcher Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many routes"	8
Ramona Mauthner	STPUAS	Visual Design & Communications	Professional staff	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities	7
Ramona Mauthner	STPUAS	Visual Design & Communications	Professional staff	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many routes"	8
KasparsŠis	VIA	Leading researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities	7
KasparsŠis	VIA	Leading researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many routes"	8
Khalid Addi	UR	Deputy Director	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Khalid Addi	UR	Deputy Director	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic partnership models and frameworks	5
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and partnership agreements	6
Agita Smitina	VIA	Head of Business Studies Field, HEI Project Lead	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Agita Smitina	VIA	Head of Business Studies Field, HEI Project Lead	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Evita Lantrate	VIA	Head of the Library	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Evita Lantrate	VIA	Head of the Library	Professional staff	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
COSMIN GABRIEL BOLEA	UEC	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
COSMIN GABRIEL BOLEA	UEC	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Hannes Van Biesbroeck	UCLL	Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Hannes Van Biesbroeck	UCLL	Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Roger Heijmans	UCLL	E ³ UDRES ² Community manager	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Roger Heijmans	UCLL	E ³ UDRES ² Community manager	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Danique van den Bergh	UCLL	Liason officer E ³ UDRES ² & Guest lecturer	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Zane Kudure	VIA	Science Secretary	Professional staff	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Zane Kudure	VIA	Science Secretary	Professional staff	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Katja Billensteiner	STPUAS	Team Member Research Funding	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Katja Billensteiner	STPUAS	Team Member Research Funding	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Oskars Java	VIA	Director of Socio-technical Systems Engineering	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Oskars Java	VIA	Director of Socio-technical Systems Engineering	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Liene Golča	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Liene Golča	VIA	Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Vice-Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Vivian García	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Māriete Balanuka	VIA	International Project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Anžela Jurāne-Brēmane	VIA	Dean of Faculty of Society and Science	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Managing Partnerships Governance and relationships m	11
Anžela Jurāne-Brēmane	VIA	Dean of Faculty of Society and Science	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Measuring and evaluating partnerships	12
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10
Agnese Davidstone	VIA	rector, associate professor, lead researcher	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Birgit Zimola	STPUAS	Team member	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing student employability through entrepreneurship education	9
Birgit Zimola	STPUAS	Team member	Professional staff	yes	yes	Creating excellent entrepreneurship education	10

Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Setting up for student entrepreneurship success	13
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	The principles for a successful university incubator or er	15
Ulrike Wieländer	STPUAS	Section Head Young talent		yes	yes	Setting up for student entrepreneurship success	13
Ulrike Wieländer	STPUAS	Section Head Young talent		yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Ulrike Wieländer	STPUAS	Section Head Young talent		yes	yes	The principles for a successful university incubator or er	15
Edmunds Jansons	VIA	Head of Master study programme		yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Nora Czako	UR	EU project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Setting up for student entrepreneurship success	13
Nora Czako	UR	EU project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Santa Vitola	VIA	Head of Vidzeme Open Innovation Centre	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Birgit Zimola	STPUAS	Team member	Professional staff	yes	yes	Setting up for student entrepreneurship success	13
Birgit Zimola	STPUAS	Team member	Professional staff	yes	yes	Supporting student start-ups and beyond	14
Birgit Zimola	STPUAS	Team member	Professional staff	yes	yes	The principles for a successful university incubator or er	15
Daniel Nunes	UPT	Assistant Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Cátia Pires	IST	Partnership manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Cátia Pires	IST	Partnership manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Championing UBC culture	17
Inês Nunes	IST	Partnership manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Andrei Crisan	UPT	Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Carla Patrocinio	IST	Tech Transfer Office Head	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Associate Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Championing UBC culture	17
Katrien Vandael	UCLL	Researcher Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building a vision for engagement	16
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Associate Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Juan Diego López Arquillo	UEC	Associate Dean	HEI leaders	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many r	19
Maria Elena Boatca Barabas	UPT	Assistant		yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many r	19
Mircea Negrut	UPT	Assoc.Prof.Dr.Eng.		yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Nora Czako	UR	EU project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Nora Czako	UR	EU project manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	University pathways to sustainability: "There are many r	19
Andra Diaconescu	UPT	As. dr. eng		yes	yes	Catalysing sustainability transformation at universities a	18
Beatriz Mendes	IST	Corporate Partnership Unit Coordinator	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Embedding industry in education	20
Beatriz Mendes	IST	Corporate Partnership Unit Coordinator	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Innovative pedagogies for impactful education	21
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Embedding industry in education	20
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Innovative pedagogies for impactful education	21
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Santa Vitola	VIA	Head of Vidzeme Open Innovation Centre	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Santa Vitola	VIA	Head of Vidzeme Open Innovation Centre	HEI leaders	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
COSMIN GABRIEL BOLEA	UEC	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
COSMIN GABRIEL BOLEA	UEC	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Rita Joana Santo Silva	IST	TTO	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Rita Joana Santo Silva	IST	TTO	Professional staff	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Nora Czako	UR	EU Project Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Nuno Almeida	IST	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Nuno Almeida	IST	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Maira Lescevic	VIA	Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Krisjanis Zakis	VIA	Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Krisjanis Zakis	VIA	Lecturer	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
Ieva Grintale	VIA	Research Assistant	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Building an Ecosystem for Entrepreneurship	23
Silvia Hafellner	STPUAS	Junior Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identify your Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	22
João Vieira	IST	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identifying and Evaluating Partners	24
João Vieira	IST	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Crafting your Partnership Approach	25
Katalin Szendrő	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identifying and Evaluating Partners	24
Katalin Szendrő	MATE	Associate Professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Crafting your Partnership Approach	25
Yuliia Kovalenko	VIA	Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Identifying and Evaluating Partners	24
Leopold Kögler-Vencour	STPUAS	International Relations		yes	yes	Identifying and Evaluating Partners	24
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Strategic Partnerships Models and Frameworks	26
Vivian Garcia	UEC	Research and Innovation Project Specialist	Professional staff	yes	yes	Negotiation and Partnership Agreements	27
Katalin Toth	MATE	Associate professor	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Measuring Collaboration Outputs, Outcomes and Impac	28
Lotte Ovaere	UCLL	Program Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Measuring Collaboration Outputs, Outcomes and Impac	28
Lotte Ovaere	UCLL	Program Manager	Professional staff	yes	yes	Communicating Impact of Collaborations	29
Anna Skruode	VIA	Head of Study programs	Professional staff	yes	yes	Developing Student Employability through Entrepreneu	30
Anna Skruode	VIA	Head of Study programs	Professional staff	yes	yes	Creating Excellent Entrepreneurship Education	31
Iran Rocha Segundo	IST	Assistant Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Developing Student Employability through Entrepreneu	30
Iran Rocha Segundo	IST	Assistant Researcher	Individual researchers & academics	yes	yes	Creating Excellent Entrepreneurship Education	31

Follow our journey

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